

SANN: A Subtree-based Attention Neural Network Model for Student Success Prediction Through Source Code Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Program code analysis is an important component in several kinds of intelligent educational systems for CS education. The ability to analyze and understand student-written code enables these systems to assess students learning and understanding of the essential programming constructs. The central issue of code analysis is a concise code representation, which enables machine learning (ML) approaches to automatically process and analyze students' code. Not surprisingly, research on developing embedding approaches that map programming code into vector representations has surged in recent years. While embedding techniques are quite well-established in the field of Natural Language Processing, the structural nature of programming codes requires special adaption of such techniques to preserve crucial semantic information. In this paper, we propose a Subtree-based Attention Neural Network (SANN) to represent novice programmer's code. Unlike existing models working on entire Abstract Syntax Trees or context paths, SANN splits each tree into a sequence of subtrees and uses an Attention-based Neural Network to encode important information from student codes in vectors while giving more attention to the important subtrees. To compare our model's effectiveness in analyzing novices' programming codes, we performed two program classification tasks: detecting correct student submissions from a single assignment and across multiple assignments. We compared SANN with Code2Vec and some well-established traditional ML models including Support Vector Machines, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Extreme Gradient Boosting. Experimental results suggest that SANN outperforms other ML models, including the state-of-the-art Code2Vec model in both student program classification tasks.

Keywords

Abstract Syntax Tree, Attention Neural Network, Code Classification, Student Success Prediction, Source Code Analysis

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1. INTRODUCTION

Analyzing codes of student programs can give a great insight into their programming knowledge and skills. In recent years, student interest in programming has been burgeoning among Computer Science and non-Computer Science students alike. It lead to a considerable increase of research on code analysis motivated by an opportunity to assist students in these introductory programming courses as well as helping instructors to understand the characteristics of students' programming learning.

Automated program analysis and student success prediction can improve learner experiences through student-facing dashboards [7] and personalized interventions for struggling students. Moreover, insights from the student success predictions can also help instructors as explanatory or exploratory tools in understanding student learning of programming languages and their applications. These insights can also help in adapting course contents, pedagogy styles, and overall learning outcomes for students [13].

A significant challenge posed by automated program analysis is identifying feature extraction approaches that can capture the structural and semantic information within students' programs [34, 22]. Moreover, a remarkable diversity of solutions generated by novice programmers while solving typical programming problems has an obstructive effect on the training process of different ML techniques [24].

A number of early studies motivated by traditional NLP-based approaches treat programming code as plain text and represent programs as bags of words or tokens. For example, token-based Information Retrieval techniques were applied in bug localization [41], and code clone detection [18, 33]. Other researchers studied the application of Latent Dirichlet Allocation [5] and Latent Semantic Indexing [10] in analyzing programming codes [35, 20]. These traditional approaches have some severe drawbacks. Though source codes have similarities with natural language texts, they should not be considered plain text and analyzed using token-based methods as they have more complex, explicit, and richer structural information [26, 25].

Following the success of different embedding techniques in NLP [16, 15], embedding techniques for source code representation and analysis are catching much attention nowa-

days. Recent studies on Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) based embedding techniques provide evidence that it can be effective in programming code representation to capture lexical and syntactical information [23, 24]. Recently, a state-of-the-art program embedding model named Code2Vec, based on an attention neural network has shown great effectiveness in analyzing expert-written source codes [4].

In this study, we propose a Subtree-based Attention Neural Network (SANN) model which works with program ASTs to create a vector representation. We split the ASTs into subtrees and perform embedding on them in a two-way approach: subtree-based embedding for each source code and node-based embedding for each subtree. From these embeddings, we generate a subtree vector for each subtree. These subtree vectors are then fed to an attention neural network to get the source code vector for each program, where the most important subtree gets the most attention. Finally, these code vectors are used to train a model that can identify the correctness of a student submission.

We used our model to perform two program classification (correct or incorrect) tasks: classification of student program submissions from a single assignment and classification of student program submissions across multiple assignments. We also compared the results with other traditional models including Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), state-of-the-art ensemble classifier Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and also with state-of-the-art embedding model Code2Vec. The experimental results showed that SANN outperformed SVM, KNN, and XGBoost in both tasks of classifying student submissions with higher accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F-1 score. It also showed that SANN had a 2% higher accuracy in classifying student submissions from a single assignment and 9% higher accuracy in classifying student submissions across multiple assignments than Code2Vec. In both tasks, SANN outperformed Code2Vec in terms of accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F-1 score.

The main contributions of this study are addressing the following three research questions (RQs):

- **RQ1:** *How well does SANN perform in classifying source codes from a single assignment?*
- **RQ2:** *How well does SANN perform in classifying source codes across multiple assignments?*
- **RQ3:** *How well does the integration of the two levels of embedding (node-based embedding and subtree-based embedding) improve the performance of the model?*

2. BACKGROUND

This study is motivated by the fields of source code representation and student success prediction to help students in their learning process and tutors in their pedagogical strategies.

2.1 Source Code Representation

Many recent studies have worked with ASTs to capture important information in analyzing source codes. In a recent study [28], utilizing ASTs from source codes and us-

ing the contextual tree decomposition algorithm, automated hints were generated for students. In another study [1], an ontological-based Java parser was used to represent the encompassing concepts of a program. To represent ordinal and hierarchical structures, [2] leveraged structural n-grams of varying sizes. Due to the vast state space and possible diversities of student solutions, most proposed feature extraction techniques are effective in small-scale programming instances.

Representing and modeling source codes using different embedding techniques has been proven effective in many recent studies. These embedding approaches have been successful in representing source codes as vector representations compatible with ML algorithms [40]. Some of these approaches combined the information retrieved from ASTs to capture knowledge regarding the lexical and syntactical structures of programming languages. Recently a state-of-the-art embedding model, Code2Vec [4] was introduced. It is an attention neural network-based model where each AST is split into paths referred to as context paths, between each pair of leaf nodes. This approach is used to successfully identify method names from codes, programmed by professional software engineers. In [23], a convolutional kernel was used to capture information from ASTs. In another study [37], a TreeLSTM model was used to capture lexical and syntactical information by generalizing a Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) network to capture tree-structured network topologies. Another novel approach [24] built a model, ast2vec, to represent source codes as vector representations by splitting up ASTs into subtrees and encoding them using a Variational Autoencoder in a recursive manner. These approaches [23, 37, 24] to representing programming codes are effective, yet they have a major drawback. They may get vulnerable to the vanishing gradient problem [14], where, during training, the gradient becomes vanishingly small and results in the incapability of properly capturing the structural information of the AST. This problem is more evident in the instance of larger and deeper ASTs [40].

Our model aims to overcome the limitations of the aforementioned previous studies [23, 37, 24] by efficiently retaining the information of subtrees while increasing the influence of more important subtrees on the final representation. Our approach constructs the code vectors neither recursively in a bottom-up approach nor by pooling all the subtree information, rather using an attention network to get a weighted average of the subtree vectors, where the most important subtrees have the most influence. We hypothesize that this approach can significantly improve the vanishing gradient problem by preserving more information and will assist in achieving better performance. Furthermore, our approach can offer more insight into the local structural information of an AST, as SANN works with the subtrees sequentially and also embeds them in a two-way embedding approach. The two-way embedding approach helps capturing the structural and syntactical information of the subtrees more efficiently than models like Code2Vec, which mostly incorporates path-based information while concatenating only the terminal leaf nodes' embedding information. This two-way embedding approach helps SANN to capture local subtree-based and node-based lexical and syntactical information along the AST sequentially.

2.2 Student Success Prediction

Student success prediction is a critical component to analyze student learning for effective interventions on an individual level and adaptive content structure. Previous research has focused on building different predictive models based on student log data, clickstream exports, textual assignments, course metadata, etc. [13]. In particular, BKT [9] and DKT-based [27] models have shown evidence to be effective in student modeling and predicting student success [29, 30, 39].

In recent years, DKT and other deep learning models have been widely used in student programming code analysis and predicting early scores and success. In [36], Recursive Neural Network was used to embed student programming submissions. In another work [21], Recent Temporal Patterns were used along with SVM and Logistic Regression model for early prediction of student difficulty. Furthermore, *programming trajectories* were also utilized in student success prediction in programming domain [32]. With the recent advancement of AST-based embedding techniques using deep learning techniques for programming data, predictive models for student programming learning has gained a new dimension. In a recent work [22], AST-based embedding models such as Code2Vec were proven to be more effective in student success prediction than other traditional ML approaches. Therefore, AST-based representational approaches can certainly help to capture inherent information from student programming data more effectively and build more powerful predictive models to analyze student learning process.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we introduce our SANN model starting with a brief introduction to ASTs. The overall architecture of the model is shown in Figure 1. We also describe different ML models with whom SANN was compared, including the state-of-the-art model Code2Vec.

3.1 Subtree-based Attention Neural Network (SANN)

3.1.1 Abstract Syntax Tree (AST)

The abstract syntactic structure of the source code is represented by the Abstract Syntax Tree [12]. It has important applications in compilers, programming languages, and software tools. As illustrated in Figure 2, an AST’s nodes correspond to the source code’s constructs or symbols. On the contrary, ASTs do not include details of source code such as delimiters or punctuations, but rather an abstract overview of the source code. It can be used to represent the structure of source code including the syntactic structure and lexical semantics, such as the method name *print* and the modifier of that method *public* in Figure 2.

3.1.2 Splitting ASTs into Subtrees

At first, the source codes were transformed into ASTs using existing tools for syntactic analysis. For each AST, we split the AST by the granularity of nodes and extracted all possible subtrees rooted at individual nodes with a preorder traversal.

The construction of the bag of subtrees for a single source code is a straightforward approach using a traverser and a

subtree constructor function ψ , where a subtree rooted at a node b can be defined as:

$$\psi(b) = \{b\} \cup \{\text{each child of } b\}$$

The traverser traverses an AST in a depth-first manner and the constructor function constructs the AST in a preorder traversal manner and adds it to the subtree sequences for that source code. For example, in Figure 2, the subtree for the node *MethodInvocation* in a preorder traversal manner results in $\{\text{MethodInvocation, System.out, Literal, "Hello world!", println}\}$, which represents the structure responsible for the printing of the string “Hello world!” in the program. This process guarantees that a new subtree is appended to the subtree sequence by the order of the source code, which is essential for preserving the semantic information in the original AST. Following these steps, we get the subtree sequences from a source code as the input of our SANN.

3.1.3 Subtree Vector Representation

After the extraction of the subtrees from a source code, these subtree sequences are fed to SANN where two types of embedding operations are performed on them: subtree-based embedding to embed each subtree of a source code and node-based embedding to embed each node of the subtree. A fully connected layer (matrix W) to get the vectors for each subtree of a sequence. This process results in training two embedding matrices for subtrees and individual nodes which are called *subtree_vocab* and *node_vocab* respectively.

$$\text{node_vocab} \in \mathbb{R}^{|X| \times d}$$

$$\text{subtree_vocab} \in \mathbb{R}^{|S| \times d}$$

Here, X is the set of all AST nodes observed during the training time and S is the set of all subtrees in the subtree sequences. The values of these matrices are randomly initialized at the start and consequently learned during the training process. From the node embedding matrix, SANN can get the knowledge of similarity between the nodes of the subtrees. Moreover, from the subtree embedding matrix, it can capture the knowledge of subtree structures and similar subtree sequences across different programming codes. Therefore, both of the embeddings help SANN to detect similar code structures across different programming codes.

Furthermore, $d \in \mathbb{N}$ is the embedding size and works as the dimensionality hyperparameter. Its value is defined empirically based on the computing time, GPU memory, and model complexity. It typically ranges from 100 to 500 in literature [4]. In our study, we kept the value of d the same for both node-based embedding and subtree-based embedding, but it can be of different values as well.

For each source code, a sequence of subtrees $S_i = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$ are extracted where each subtree $s_i = \{x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{in}\}$ is a sequence of nodes from that subtree rooted at x_{i1} such that $x_{ij} \in X$ and $s_i \in S$. Each node of a subtree is looked up and mapped to its corresponding embedding from the *node_vocab* matrix. We get *node_embedded*: the node-based embedding for a whole subtree obtained from summing up each node embedding of the subtree. We could have chosen to concatenate node embeddings or created another Attention layer to merge these node embeddings into a single vector for each subtree. Both of these approaches would

Figure 1: Architecture of SANN

have required more training time and resources and made the model more complex. Therefore, we choose a simpler way and generate *node_embedded* by summing each node embedding of the subtree [3].

$$node_embedded(s_i) = \sum_j node_vocab(x_{ij})$$

In a similar fashion, the subtree-based embedding is done for a subtree by looking up the *subtree_vocab* matrix to get *subtree_embedded* for a subtree.

$$subtree_embedded(s_i) = subtree_vocab(s_i)$$

After getting both the *node_embedded* and *subtree_embedded* for each subtree, they are concatenated to a single embedded vector: $e_i \in \mathbb{R}^{2d}$ representing the merged embedded vectors from node-based embedding and subtree-based embedding.

$$e_i = [node_embedded, subtree_embedded] \in \mathbb{R}^{2d}$$

Since the embedded vector e_i consists of the concatenation of the embeddings from the node-based and subtree-based approaches, we use a fully connected layer to combine these components and generate a vector from each embedded vector e_i which we refer to as subtree vector sv_i . Using the same learned combination function, this is done independently for each embedded vector e_i . This allows SANN to generate a subtree vector sv_i by combining the information from node-based embedding and subtree-based embedding. A subtree vector sv_i is the output of the fully connected layer from an embedded vector e_i which is computed as:

$$sv_i = \tanh(W \cdot e_i)$$

Figure 2: Abstract Syntax Tree for a simple Java code snippet

Here, \tanh is the hyperbolic tangent activation function which is a monotonic function and the range is from -1 to 1. This results in increased expressiveness of the model. The W is a learned weight matrix where $W \in \mathbb{R}^{2d \times 2d}$. The height of W determines the size of the subtree vector which is kept the same as e_i for convenience. Thus, the fully connected layer converts the embedded vector e_i into subtree vector sv_i by multiplying e_i with the weight matrix W and applying \tanh activation function element-wise.

3.1.4 Vector Representation of Source Code Using Attention

After getting all the subtree vectors for an AST, SANN uses an attention neural network to compress them into one single vector c . The attention mechanism calculates one scalar weight per subtree vector sv_i and aggregates all the subtree vectors by taking the weighted average. An attention vector $av \in \mathbb{R}^{2d}$ is learned simultaneously while training, starting from a random initialization. For each subtree vector sv_i in an AST, the attention weight a_i is calculated by the normalized inner product of the global attention vector av , and the subtree vector sv_i . Attention weight a_i for each subtree vector sv_i is calculated using a standard softmax function so that all the attention weights have a sum of 1, and the exponents in the softmax equation yield positive attention weights. Calculating an attention weight a_i using the softmax function is as follows:

$$a_i = \frac{\exp(sv_i^T \cdot av)}{\sum_{j=1}^n \exp(sv_j^T \cdot av)}$$

The vector representation of a whole source code snippet $c \in \mathbb{R}^{2d}$ is then calculated by calculating the weighted average of the subtree vectors using attention weights. This is a linear combination of the subtree vectors $\{sv_1, sv_2, \dots, sv_n\}$ based on the importance as determined by the attention network:

$$\text{Source code vector, } c = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \cdot sv_i$$

In this way, the most important subtree gets the most attention in the calculation of the source code vector. The attention weights are calculated during the training process with respect to all other subtrees from the subtree sequence of a source code.

3.1.5 Prediction

For the program classification task, SANN uses a softmax layer to classify codes into correct or incorrect using the source code vector $c = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{2d}\}$ as input. The output dimension of the softmax layer $\in \mathbb{R}^{|Y|}$, where Y is the set of classes to be predicted. These output $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{|Y|}\}$ can be viewed as the probability of the source code belonging to each class y_i of $Y = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{|Y|}\}$ in a categorical way. The mathematical equation for this calculation is:

$$p_i = \frac{\exp(c_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^{2d} \exp(c_i)}$$

Therefore, the probability of a source code belonging to the class y_i is p_i . The softmax layer outputs these probabilities in the range of (0, 1). Finally, we can classify the source code as the class having the maximum probability of p_i .

3.2 Traditional Machine Learning Models

We also implemented Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) to observe how well our SANN model performs against these Machine Learning (ML) models. SVM is a widely used classifier that creates a decision boundary to separate data points into respective classes [31]. The *kernel* in SVM determines the nature of this decision boundary and the hyperparameter C is a penalty term for each misclassification. If C is low, the penalty for misclassification is also low. Hence, a decision boundary with a larger margin would have to trade-off with a higher number of misclassifications. KNN is a supervised, instance-based, nonparametric algorithm [17]. It classifies each data point by measuring the distance from other nearest neighbors, which is defined as the parameter $n_neighbors$. The distance between two data points can be measured in two ways: Euclidean distance or Manhattan distance. This can be defined by the parameter p . In brief, KNN visits every data point and calculates the conditional probability of that data point belonging to each class. XGBoost is based on gradient boosted decision trees [8]. It has outperformed other ensemble techniques recently due to its parallelization and algorithmic enhancements. The parameter $gamma$ helps the model to be conservative so that each split of nodes in the tree results in a minimum reduction in the loss function, and max_depths restricts the depth of the tree to avoid overfitting. For preparing the numerical inputs from source code for these traditional ML models, we have used the TF-IDF feature extraction technique [19].

3.3 Code2Vec

Code2Vec [4] learns code embeddings by splitting an AST into context paths $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{|P|}\}$ which are leaf to leaf paths of the AST, where leaves are referred to as terminals. These context paths are constructed as $p_i = \{terminal_{leaf}^1, path, terminal_{leaf}^2\}$. Strings of different context paths are mapped to different numbers. These encoded context paths work as the inputs of the Code2Vec model. Unlike SANN, Code2Vec does a node-based embedding on the terminal nodes only and the path is also embedded in a similar manner. These terminal and path embeddings are then concatenated and converted into context vectors $\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{|R|}\}$. The context vectors construct a matrix $E \in \mathbb{R}^{e \times |R|}$. Then these context vectors are fed into a soft attention layer with $W_{al} \in \mathbb{R}^{e \times 1}$ matrix [38], which later helps in calculating the attention weight α_i for each context vector: $\alpha = SoftMax(W_{al}^T \cdot E)$. Then code vector for a whole source code snippet is calculated by taking the dot product of each context vector e_i with attention weight α_i . The prediction task is done based on the code vector passing through an output Softmax layer.

4. DATASET

In this study, we obtained the dataset from CodeWorkout¹, which is an online platform for Java programming. This web-based platform offers instructors to design and offer their courses and students to practice programming [11]. CodeWorkout logs student submissions. Students receive their scores based on test case passing. Students can also submit multiple solutions for the same assignment. For

¹<https://codeworkout.cs.vt.edu/>

Table 1: Dataset overview

Properties	Task 1	Task 2
Compilable submissions	1850	9403
Correct	344	3162
Incorrect	1506	6241

this work, we tried to evaluate our model in two scenarios: task 1: Classifying student submissions from the same programming assignment, and task 2: Classifying student submissions across multiple programming assignments. For task 2, we picked multiple assignments’ submissions which include assignments named *caughtSpeeding*, *isEverywhere*, *sortaSum*, *int1To10*, *answerCell*, *squirrelPlay*, *alarmClock*, and *cigarParty*. These assignments evaluate student knowledge of method declaration, loop, array, arithmetic operations, logical expressions, data types, conditionals, nested conditional statements, etc. For task 1, we picked all the student submissions from the assignment *caughtSpeeding*. The dataset consists of one semester: Spring 2019. We discarded the source codes that are uncompileable since these cannot be easily converted into ASTs. Student submissions were marked as correct if got a score of 1 out of 1 and incorrect otherwise. Table 1 outlines the dataset in brief. From Table 1, we can see that the dataset has a class imbalance between correct and incorrect submissions.

5. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

In this section, we evaluate our proposed SANN model in the task of programming classification. We have performed this task in two ways: classification of a single assignment, and classification across multiple assignments. The dataset was split randomly into 80%-20% for training and testing purposes respectively. Due to the imbalance characteristic of the dataset, we kept the ratio of the number of correct and incorrect submissions in the training and testing data identical. For parsing the Java source codes into ASTs, we used the `javalang` tool² which is an open-source python library providing a lexer and parser for Java programming language.

5.1 Evaluation Metrics

The performance of the models can be measured using the accuracy metric. Accuracy helps us to understand the portion of the programs that were correctly classified. However, in the case of a dataset like ours, it can be misleading to use accuracy as the only evaluation metric can be misleading for an imbalanced dataset like ours with a ratio of 1:2 (correct:incorrect). Therefore, the performance of the models was measured using Precision, Recall, and F1-score along with the accuracy of the models. Precision helps to understand the proportion of positive class predictions which were truly correct out of all the positive predictions. Recall is also called sensitivity, which quantifies out of all the correct classes in the dataset, how many were predicted correctly. F1-score sets the trade-off of Precision and Recall by taking their harmonic mean.

²<https://github.com/c2nes/javalang>

5.2 Experimental Settings

5.2.1 Traditional Machine Learning models

We performed a grid search with 5-fold cross-validation to find the optimal hyperparameter values for SVM, KNN, and XGBoost. For SVM, we set the *kernel* to “*poly*” from the set {“*linear*”, “*poly*”, “*rbf*”}, and *C* to 10 from the set {0.1, 1, 10}. For KNN, we set *n_neighbors* to 10 from the set {5, 10, 15} and *p* to 2 (Manhattan distance) from the set {1, 2}. For XGBoost, we set the value of *gamma* to 1 from the set {1, 5, 9}, *n_estimators* to 180, and *max_depth* to 10 from the set {3, 6, 10}.

5.2.2 SANN

Training deep learning models require more time and resources than traditional ML models. Therefore we did not perform any grid search to tune the hyperparameters, rather we changed those manually to get the best output. We set the embedding size to 128 for both node-based and subtree-based embedding from {64, 128, 256}, which led the source code vectors for each Java source to be of size 256. We have manually padded the number of subtrees for each source code and the length of each subtree so that the maximum number of subtrees for a source code and the maximum length of a subtree were both 100. We also experimented with other values from the set {50, 100, 150, 200}.

5.2.3 Code2Vec

For the Code2Vec model, the linear and embedding layer dimensions were set to the default value of 128. We manually padded the context paths for each code submission to 100.

For both SANN and Code2Vec models, batch size was set to 128. The maximum number of epochs was set to 200, with a patience of 50 for early stopping during the training process. All of the weight matrices are learned during the training process using the Adam optimizer [6] with learning rate 0.001. The weights of both models were not updated in the later phases.

5.3 Research Questions

Our evaluation aims to answer the following research questions (RQs):

RQ1: *How well does SANN perform in classifying source codes from a single assignment?*

This RQ addresses program classification task 1 as mentioned in section 4. For classifying source codes obtained from a single assignment from the CodeWorkout data, we had a total number of 1480 submissions in the training set and 370 submissions in the testing set. We evaluated our SANN model using this data and compared the performance with other traditional ML models such as SVM, KNN, and XGBoost. We also compared it with Code2Vec. The results are demonstrated in Table 2.

From Table 2, we can see that traditional ML models could not do better than AST-based deep learning models. Though XGBoost and KNN showed the same accuracy, we can get a better idea from the F1-score due to the imbalance characteristic of the dataset. From the F1-score value, we can see that XGBoost had a better performance than KNN. Our

Table 2: Performance comparison for classifying student submissions from a single assignment

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
SVM	0.85	0.78	0.63	0.63
KNN	0.86	0.79	0.66	0.70
XGBoost	0.86	0.76	0.77	0.76
Code2Vec	0.89	0.84	0.77	0.80
SANN	0.92	0.92	0.80	0.86

model SANN outperformed the state-of-the-art Code2Vec model with an accuracy of 0.92. That means SANN is able to distinguish correct source codes from a single assignment with almost 2% higher accuracy than the Code2Vec model. It also showed the highest Precision, Recall, and F1-score with values of 0.92, 0.80, and 0.86 respectively whereas for Code2Vec, Precision, Recall, and F1-score value were 0.84, 0.77, and 0.80 respectively. Therefore SANN outperformed Code2Vec not only by accuracy but also in the case of classifying imbalanced data for a single assignment of students.

RQ2: *How well does SANN perform in classifying source codes across multiple assignments?*

This RQ addresses program classification task 2 as mentioned in section 4. In this task of classifying source codes obtained from multiple assignments from the CodeWorkout data, we had a total number of 7522 submissions in the training set and 1881 submissions in the testing set. We evaluated our SANN model using this data and compared the performance with other traditional ML models such as SVM, KNN, and XGBoost. We also compared it with Code2Vec. The results are demonstrated in Table 3.

From Table 3, XGBoost was the best among the traditional ML models but could not beat the Code2Vec model. In both tasks, the traditional ML models performed worse than the two AST-based deep learning models. These traditional models depend on shallow semantic features, based on the sequence of tokens in the source code. This makes it difficult to capture any structural information correctly because, in the case of student codes, token names may vary from one submission to another, i.e. variable names can be a , b , i , j , etc. Furthermore, We can see that our model SANN outperformed the state-of-the-art Code2Vec model with an accuracy of 0.86. That means SANN is able to distinguish correct source codes from multiple assignments with about 9% higher accuracy than the Code2Vec model. It also surpasses all other models in terms of Precision, Recall and F1-score with values of 0.85, 0.83, and 0.84 respectively, whereas the second-best performance was of Code2Vec with Precision, Recall, and F1-score value of 0.76, 0.76, and 0.76 respectively.

RQ3: *How well does the integration of the two levels of embedding (node-based embedding and subtree-based embedding) improve the performance of the model?*

Our SANN model adopts a two-way embedding approach: node-based embedding for each subtree and subtree-based embedding for each source code and aggregates this informa-

Table 3: Performance comparison for classifying student submissions across multiple assignments

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
SVM	0.74	0.71	0.70	0.70
KNN	0.75	0.72	0.70	0.71
XGBoost	0.77	0.75	0.74	0.74
Code2Vec	0.79	0.76	0.76	0.76
SANN	0.86	0.85	0.83	0.84

tion to generate the source code vectors using an attention mechanism. However, it is still unknown to what extent our two-way embedding approach improves the performance of the SANN model rather than adopting a one-way embedding (only node-based embedding or only subtree-based embedding) approach. In order to verify and test this claim, we train our SANN model in three ways: with only node-based embedding, with only subtree-based embedding, with both node-based embedding and subtree-based embedding. This experiment is conducted with task 2, which is student program classification across multiple assignments. From Table 4, we can see that SANN with only subtree-based embedding outperformed the node-embedding approach with an accuracy of 0.83. But with the two-way embedding approach, SANN showed the highest accuracy of 0.86. Furthermore, it also outperforms other design choices in terms of Precision, Recall, and F1-score as well with values of 0.85, 0.83, and 0.84 respectively. Therefore, the two-way embedding approach shows a significant improvement in the performance of SANN in classifying student programs.

The experimental results suggest that SANN can capture student program information efficiently from ASTs because of its robust architecture. Splitting each AST into a sequence of subtrees and embedding them following the two-way embedding approach helps SANN to capture local subtree-based and node-based lexical and syntactical information along the AST sequentially. From the node-based embedding approach, SANN can get the knowledge of similarity between the nodes of the subtrees. Moreover, from the subtree-based embedding approach, it can capture the knowledge of subtree structures and similar subtree sequences across different programming codes. The attention mechanism used to embed all the subtree vectors into a single source code vector allows SANN to give more attention to the most important region of the AST. This helps to encode the most important structural information of the AST with greater attention and restricts the effect of the vanishing gradient problem.

6. CONCLUSION

In this study, we have presented a Subtree-based Attention Neural Network (SANN) model to analyze arbitrary-sized students' programming codes and represent them into fixed-length vectors by embedding their lexical and syntactical information. The core idea is to split a program into a sequence of subtrees, embed them following a two-way embedding approach: subtree-based embedding for each subtree, and node-based embedding for each node of a subtree and get source code vector using a soft attention mechanism. We evaluated SANN on two program classification

Table 4: Performance comparison for two-way embedding approach of SANN

Embedding approach	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
node-based embedding	0.75	0.72	0.71	0.71
subtree-based embedding	0.83	0.82	0.82	0.82
two-way embedding (node-based+ subtree-based embedding)	0.86	0.85	0.83	0.84

(correct or incorrect) tasks: classifying student submissions from a single programming assignment and classifying student submissions across multiple programming assignments. The experimental results provide evidence that SANN outperformed not only traditional ML models like SVM, KNN, and XGBoost, but also state-of-the-art embedding model Code2Vec in terms of accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score values. It also showed that the two-way embedding approach improved the performance of SANN compared to using a one-way embedding approach (only node-based embedding or only subtree-based embedding). The small size of the dataset and its class-imbalance characteristic suggests that SANN is less data-hungry and better capable of handling imbalanced data than Code2Vec. In Educational Data Mining area, it is hard to collect larger datasets and we tend to end up collecting relatively smaller datasets. Consequently, data-hungry models cannot perform good on analyzing classroom-sized smaller datasets, which is a crucial hurdle in student data analysis.

Our work has some limitations at the current stage. SANN currently extracts all possible subtrees of an AST, which poses time and resource constraints when generalizing for larger and deeper ASTs. This is important since, with the increased number of unique subtrees, the size of the embedding metrics would also grow. Moreover, it may lead to information loss for a deeper AST due to a large number of subtrees in a subtree sequence. SANN may not be able to capture the information of the lower part of the AST properly by its sequential analysis manner due to the maximum number of subtrees constraint for a specific source code. In the future, we want to regulate the subtree extraction process so that we can get fewer, smaller, and more meaningful subtrees from an AST. For example, an evolutionary algorithm can be used to obtain the most optimized depth for each subtree. Extracting non-overlapping subtrees can also fasten the subtree-extraction process and help reduce the number of subtrees per program. This will assist the subtree-based embedding to capture similar subtree information more efficiently. Furthermore, we want to train our model with more data and larger ASTs to make it more robust in analyzing student codes.

This work is a stepping stone in building a robust Subtree-based Attention Neural Network model to analyze student codes in a more efficient and effective way than existing AST-based deep learning models. This approach focuses on capturing local structural information of ASTs and also on generalizability for larger and deeper ASTs without vanishing gradient problem. It aims to assist with applications in different student program-related tasks to help tutors and students.

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